

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V) with N-Hydroxy-N-p-Chlorophenyl-N'-(3-chloro-4-methyl) phenylbenzamidine**

PRAMOD KUMAR SHARMA and RAJENDRA K. MISHRA*

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur-492 002

Manuscript received 26 March 1979, revised 30 July 1979, accepted 9 July 1980

A highly selective spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of vanadium(V) at ppm level. A chloroform solution of N-hydroxy-N-p-chlorophenyl-N'-(3-chloro-4-methyl)phenylbenzamidine quantitatively extracts vanadium(V) as blue-violet complex from 0.5-10.0M acetic acid media. The complex shows a broad absorption maxima at 570-590 nm having the value for molar absorptivity to be 4210 l.mole⁻¹cm⁻¹. The sensitivity of the colour reaction is 0.011 µg of vanadium(V) cm⁻². The 1:2 (vanadium : reagent) complex adheres to Beer's law in the range 20 µg to 300 µg/25 ml. The influence of various experimental factors such as time, temperature, concentration of the reagent and the presence of diverse ions, etc. have been studied.

SINCE the introduction of N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylbenzamidine as a new class of organo-analytical reagent by Satyanarayana and Mishra¹, several analogous compounds have been synthesised² and applied for the gravimetric and spectrophotometric determination of a number of transition metal ions³⁻⁵. As compared to the established reagents such as cupferron, N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine, α-benzoinoxime, 8-hydroxyquinoline⁶ and 3-hydroxy-1, 3-diphenyl triozene⁷, the hydroxyamidine functional grouping I, provides wider scope as due to great synthetic flexibility, substitution at all the three available sites can be made with a view to modifying the complexing property of the reagent

The newly synthesised reagent, N-hydroxy-N-p-chlorophenyl-N'-(3-chloro-4-methyl)phenylbenzamidine has been employed for the highly selective spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) after extraction into chloroform from 0.5-10.0M acetic acid media. The present method, which is simple, rapid and sensitive can be compared favourably with any of the methods for vanadium(V)⁸⁻⁹ so far as selectivity is concerned.

Experimental

Apparatus: An ECIL UV-VIS spectrophotometer GS-865 equipped with 1 cm matched quartz

and silica cells was employed for absorbance measurements.

Standard vanadium(V) solution: A stock solution of vanadium(V) was prepared by dissolving ammonium meta vanadate (BDH. A.R.) in double distilled water. The vanadium content of this solution was determined volumetrically¹⁰.

Preparation of N-hydroxy-N-p-chlorophenyl-N'-(3-chloro-4-methyl)phenylbenzamidine:

The reagent was prepared by the condensation of equimolar quantities of N-(3-chloro-4-methyl)phenylbenzimidoyl chloride and N-p-chlorophenyl hydroxylamine in ether medium². The resulting hydrochloride was filtered and treated with dilute ammonia to get the free base. The pale-yellow crystals of the reagent were obtained upon crystallisation from petroleum ether: benzene (1:2) mixture. m.p. 168-169°, yield: 50%. (Found: C, 64.50; N, 7.38; H, 4.48 percent. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₆N₂OCl₂; C, 64.69; N, 7.54; H, 4.31 percent.) A 0.1% W/V solution of the reagent in chloroform was employed for extraction purposes.

Procedure: Place an aliquot of the solution containing 100 µg of vanadium(V) in a 60 ml separating funnel. To this add required amount of acetic acid (so adjust the acidity between 0.5-10.0 M) and sufficient water to bring the total volume to 25 ml. Add 10 ml of chloroform solution of the reagent and shake vigorously for 1 min, separate the coloured chloroform layer containing the vanadium complex and collect over anhydrous

** Presented at the Annual Convention of Chemist, 1978 held at Waltair.

* Senior author.

sodium sulphate in a small beaker. Extract the aqueous phase with 2×4 ml portions of chloroform and mix with the main extract. Transfer the combined extracts into a 25 ml volumetric flask and dilute to volume with chloroform. Measure the absorbance at 580 nm against chloroform as blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra : The absorption spectra of vanadium(V)-HCPCMPB complex and reagent are shown in Fig. 1. The vanadium-HCPCMPB complex show λ_{\max} at 580 nm with ϵ , $4210 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (in 0.5-10.0 M acetic acid). The reagent has negligible absorbance in the region 450-700 nm.

Fig. 1. Absorption Spectra :

- (A) (-○-○-○-) 4 ppm Vanadium + 0.009M HCPCMPB in chloroform.
 (B) (-●-●-●-) 0.009M HCPCMPB in chloroform.

Effect of variables : The acidity was maintained with glacial acetic acid and optimum acidity range was found to be 0.5-10.0 M acetic acid. A 7 fold molar excess of reagent was adequate for complete extraction of vanadium(V). Addition of excess reagent had no adverse effect. Order of addition of reagent was not critical.

A time of 1 min. was sufficient for complete extraction of vanadium(V). Variation in temperature from 20 to 35° and aqueous phase from 10-60 ml did not affect the position of absorption band and absorbance of coloured system.

Beer's law, optimum concentration range, molar absorptivity and precision : The system obeyed

Beer's law upto 0.8 to 12.0 ppm. The optimum concentration range on the basis of Ringbom¹¹ plot was found to be 2.8 to 10 ppm. The effective molar absorptivity was $4210 \pm 50 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a Sandell's¹² sensitivity $0.011 \mu\text{g metal per cm}^2$.

The mean absorbance value of 15 samples each containing 4 ppm of vanadium(V) was found to be 0.33 at 580 nm. The standard and relative standard deviations were $\pm 3.27 \times 10^{-3}$ absorbance unit and $\pm 0.99\%$ respectively.

Composition : In V(V)-HCPCMPB complex, the ratio of vanadium to reagent was determined by molar ratio¹³, slope ratio¹⁴ and Job's method of continuous variations¹⁵. The results obtained showed the formation of 1 : 2 (metal : reagent) complex in chloroform.

TABLE 1—TOLERANCE LIMIT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE DETERMINATION OF 4 ppm VANADIUM(V) AT 6M ACETIC ACID

Ions added	Tolerated* amount ppm	Ions added	Tolerated* amount ppm
Fe ³⁺	800	Ti ⁴⁺	60
Cu ²⁺	500	Mo ⁶⁺	300
Co ²⁺	700	W ⁶⁺	20
Ni ²⁺	700	Al ³⁺	600
Zn ²⁺	1000	Cr ³⁺	600
Cd ²⁺	1000	Th ⁴⁺	800
Mn ²⁺	800	Th ⁴⁺	800
Pb ²⁺	1200	Arsenate	400
Ag ⁺	700	Citrate	600
Sb ³⁺	600	Tartrate	600
Nb ⁵⁺	100	Fluoride	500
Ta ⁵⁺	200	Iodide	600

* error causing 2%.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of foreign ions for determination of 4 ppm vanadium(V) was studied at 6 M acetic acid concentration of the aqueous phase. Varying amount of the foreign ions were taken with a fixed amount of vanadium and the colour was developed and measured as described in earlier procedure.

Chloride, bromide, nitrate, sulphate, ammonium, phthalate, borate, triethanolamine, lanthanoid elements, alkaline and alkali-earth elements did not interfere upto 2000 ppm. The tolerance limits of other ions are shown in Table 1.

Application of method in B. C. S. Steels :

The validity of method was tested in two tungsten steels 64a, 241/1 and tungsten free vanadium steel 252 obtained from the Bureau of Analysed Samples, Ltd., Newham Hall, Middlesbrough, Yorks.

The results obtained are shown in Table 2.

Delhi for the award of a fellowship to one of them (PKS).

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN B.C.S.* STEELS

Name of steel	Vanadium ^a found	Certified value	Standard deviation
64a	1.557	1.57	±0.01058
Alloy steel 241/1	1.56	1.57	±0.00648
High speed steel 252	0.454	0.46	±0.00845
Low alloy steel			

* British Chemical Standards.
 a Average of 5 determinations.

A weighed quantity of sample containing 3 mg of vanadium was dissolved in dilute nitric acid (30%). The hydrated tungstic oxide was filtered through Whatmann filter paper No. 42. The oxides of nitrogen were removed by boiling and vanadium content of sample was determined by the recommended procedure.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. G. Tandon, Head, Dept. of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur, for providing research facilities and to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New

References

1. K. SATYANARAYANA and R. K. MISHRA, *Anal. Chem.*, 1974, **46**, 1609.
2. K. K. DEB and R. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 178.
3. K. SATYANARAYANA and R. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 63, 469, 928.
4. R. S. KHARSAN, K. S. PATEL and R. K. MISHRA, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 50, 254.
5. K. S. PATEL, K. K. DEB and R. K. MISHRA, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1979, **52**, 595.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co., Ltd., London, 1964.
7. M. O. SOGANI and S. C. BHATTACHARYA, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 81, 1616.
8. G. SVEHLA and G. TOLD, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 755.
9. A. K. MAJUMDAR, "N-Benzoyl-Phenyl-hydroxylamine and its analogues", Pergamon, Oxford, 1972.
10. G. CHARLOT and D. BRZIER, *Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*, Interscience, New York, 1959.
11. A. RINGBOM, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1938, **115**, 332.
12. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", p. 83, Interscience Publication, Inc. New York, 1959.
13. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
14. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
15. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, **9**, 113.